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TYPES OF ACCOMMODATION FACILITIES IN UZBEKISTAN AND THEIR CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract: This article provides a comprehensive analysis of accommodation facilities, focusing on their various types, defining characteristics, and fundamental essence within the tourism and hospitality sector. Special attention is given to identifying the structural and functional features that distinguish different categories of accommodation, including hotels, motels, hostels, guesthouses, and alternative lodging options. The study also explores the economic, social, and service-related roles these facilities play in enhancing tourism infrastructure and guest satisfaction. In addition, scientifically grounded proposals and recommendations have been developed to improve the classification system of accommodation facilities. These are aimed at increasing operational efficiency, standardizing service quality, and ensuring alignment with international benchmarks and sustainable tourism practices.

Key words: accommodation facilities, types, characteristics, essence, classification, hospitality industry, service efficiency, tourism infrastructure.

INTRODUCTION

As a result of the new reforms being implemented in our country, the tourism industry is being elevated to the status of a strategic sector of the state. This process has laid the groundwork for the construction and commissioning of accommodation facilities that meet many international standards, as well as the development of new tourist destinations.

The government of Uzbekistan is creating an attractive investment environment aimed at modernizing existing tourist infrastructure and building new accommodation facilities—particularly hotels—according to advanced international models.

Consequently, substantial investments are now being directed even to those regions with previously untapped or underdeveloped tourism potential. Foreign investors are being actively attracted to these projects. This is because the accelerated development of the tourism industry—which has now attained the status of a strategic sector of our economy—is crucial for increasing employment, utilizing labor resources in remote areas, boosting foreign currency inflows, expanding the country's economic capabilities, making full use of regional economic potential, and most importantly, promoting Uzbekistan's positive image on the global stage.

To support the development of the tourism sector, several important decisions have recently been made. Notably, the State Committee for Tourism has been established under the Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection, and Climate Change of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and new opportunities and benefits have been introduced to further accelerate the sector's growth [1]. In addition, the Strategy for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2025–2030 [2] recognizes tourism as a strategic branch of the national economy and marks the beginning of a new qualitative stage of development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

At present, numerous scientific studies dedicated to the concept of “classification” can be found in specialized academic literature. These works interpret and define the term in various ways; however, all of them emphasize a central point: the services are oriented toward consumer needs. Based on these conclusions, we briefly analyze the views of several authors and present our own considerations regarding the concept of classification.

According to N.M. Malykh, hotel classification is a set of characteristics and definitions of certain services, which reflect the ability to satisfy specific features and requirements related to accommodation, lodging, dining, and other services provided to guests [3]. In this context, improving service quality is not always linked solely

to the additional features of services, but also to the increase in associated costs. It is noted that high-quality services often come with higher prices, and this aspect is not always taken into account. Therefore, the financial capabilities of hotels become a determining factor.

L.N. Semerkova and others argue that hotel classification must comply with established standards and belong to a certain type, which must be confirmed by a firm, corporation, association, or unified network [4].

It is important to note that there is currently no unified understanding among scholars regarding hotel classification as a management object. In our view, hotel classification represents a defined set of characteristics as outlined in standards, and these characteristics reflect the specific types of services expected by clients. These characteristics are intrinsic to various categories of accommodation facilities and are determined by their quality parameters. Within the hotel industry, classification ensures that the guests' needs for lodging, dining, and various auxiliary and complementary services are adequately met. From this perspective, classification carries normative characteristics established by the relevant standards and can only be compared and evaluated based on similar types of services.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology involved analyzing scholarly opinions regarding the quality and efficiency of service delivery in hotels. The study utilized methods such as observation, comparison, empirical research, systematic and comparative analysis, statistical classification, and expert evaluation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Accommodation facilities are classified based on their designated function, location and positioning, operating time, level of technical equipment, the condition of their physical infrastructure and room stock, capacity, quality level of services provided, and types of visitors served. Functionally, accommodation facilities are divided into two main categories: transit and destination-based accommodations.

Transit accommodation facilities are designed to serve guests during short-term stays or stopovers. In contrast, destination accommodations are those specialized in certain travel destinations. For example, luxurious and star-rated hotels in capital cities, major urban centers, or tourist hubs; sanatorium-resort accommodations in mountainous or coastal areas; and small family-run guesthouses commonly found in various regions of the country.

According to their physical location, accommodation facilities can be classified as urban, suburban, rural, mountainous, forested, or riverside.

Seasonality is a natural feature of tourism. Therefore, accommodation facilities can be categorized by operating periods as follows:

- Year-round operation

- Seasonal operation

- Weekend-only operation

- Time-specific operation (24-hour, daytime only, or limited hours)

In the hotel industry, one of the most significant indicators is the size of the room inventory. Accommodation facilities can be classified according to the number of rooms as follows:

- Large: more than 200 rooms

- Medium: from 51 to 200 rooms

- Small: from 16 to 50 rooms

- Mini: up to 15 rooms

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the classification of accommodation facilities is denoted by a star rating system, ranging across five levels. The highest rating is five stars, while the lowest is one star. The reason that the classification system applies not only to hotels but also to all accommodation facilities is because the star rating is defined by the National Standard of Uzbekistan — "Tourism Services. Accommodation Facilities. Point-Based Classification System," O'zDSt 125:2024. According to this standard, not only hotels but also sanatoriums and other accommodation types may be awarded a star category.

As shown in Table 1, currently 74 hotels and 2 sanatoriums across the country have received official star classifications.

It is evident that in major cities, the number of star-rated hotels is relatively high. At present, both foreign and domestic tourists are increasingly demanding accommodation facilities that operate under star-rated service standards. As the number of inbound tourists continues to rise annually, so too does the share of users who choose internationally recognized and prestigious hotel brands that meet global standards.

Table 1 provides data on the number of foreign tourists who have visited Uzbekistan in recent years.

Table 1. Classification of Accommodation Facilities in Uzbekistan

No	Region Name	Number of Classified Hotels	Number of Classified Sanatoriums
1	Republic of Karakalpakstan	1	–
2	Andijan Region	1	–
3	Bukhara Region	6	–
4	Jizzakh Region	0	–
5	Navoi Region	2	–
6	Namangan Region	2	–
7	Samarkand Region	14	–
8	Sirdarya Region	1	–
9	Surkhandarya Region	4	–
10	Fergana Region	8	–
11	Kashkadarya Region	0	–
12	Khorezm Region	5	–
13	Tashkent Region	2	2
14	Tashkent City	30	–
	Total	76	2

Table 2. Foreign Tourists Visiting Uzbekistan

No	Regions and Countries	Number of Foreign Tourists by Year	
		2020	
1	Total Visitors	1,504,126	
2	From Neighboring Countries	1,350,372	
3	From Other CIS Countries	89,980	
4	From Other Countries	63,774	

Based on the table above, it can be observed that in 2024, 83.5% of foreign tourists visiting Uzbekistan came from neighboring countries, 9.2% from other CIS countries, and 7.3% from non-CIS countries. Moreover, due to the recent increase in the number of tourism demonstration sites in the country, the average length of stay for tourists has reached 7–8 days.

According to the composition and specialization of visitors, accommodation facilities are categorized as follows:

- for tourism,
- sports and physical wellness,
- children's and youth tourism,
- student groups,
- family tourism,
- elderly tourists,
- people with physical disabilities,
- children-specific accommodations,
- business travelers or those on official visits (see Table 3).

Accommodation facilities may also be classified based on the type of building in which the room inventory is located:

- in standalone buildings (excluding private individual houses);
- in private individual homes;
- in apartments within multi-story residential buildings;
- in other types of buildings or in sections of buildings and structures.

Naturally, the specialization of accommodation facilities should reflect the purpose of tourists' visits, as well as their age, religion, and ethnic background. In recent years, as the number of public events held in Uzbekistan has increased, the number and proportion of young foreign tourists have also grown. It has become a norm to organize national events according to a calendar plan, which has contributed to the growing influx of

young tourists. Tour operators and travel agents have actively intensified efforts to attract young tourists from foreign countries to participate in events held in Uzbekistan, which is clearly reflected in the rising share of youth tourism, as shown in the next table.

All these efforts are clearly aimed at increasing the flow of tourists to the country and boosting the export of tourism services.

In conclusion, hotel classification is determined on one hand by the normative standards established for different types of accommodation facilities, and on the other hand, by consumers' individual needs, expectations, preferences, and purchasing capacities.

The classification of hotels is influenced by the following factors:

Condition of material and technical infrastructure: includes convenient architectural layout and high-quality finishing of buildings, provision of public areas and hotel rooms with comfortable furniture and furnishings, availability of high-quality bedding and linens, and use of modern, high-performance kitchen equipment.

Advanced service technologies: methods and procedures for cleaning public areas and guest rooms, systems for check-in and billing, and standardized rules (recipes and preparation techniques) for food and beverages in cafes, bars, restaurants, etc.

Cultural and social quality: behavior and attitude of hotel staff towards guests, including professional qualifications and competence, and their readiness to deliver prompt, polite, and high-quality service.

Table 3. Composition of visitors by age group (unit of measurement: thousand persons)

Age Group	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
0 to 18 years	611.8	140.7	270.9	723.3	1,064.5	1,712.0
19 to 30 years	1,315.9	285.8	312.6	846.5	1,000.2	1,521.6
31 to 55 years	3,458.6	787.5	935.4	2,593.4	3,192.7	4,924.9
Over 55 years	1,362.2	290.2	362.5	1,069.6	1,368.7	2,126.5
TOTAL	6,748.5	1,504.1	1,881.3	5,232.8	6,626.3	10,285.0

Information culture: ensuring the timely delivery of comprehensive information to consumers, with attention to its completeness, objectivity, reliability, and up-to-dateness, among other qualities.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The following key directions can be identified to improve the classification of hotels:

Modernizing, coordinating, and improving the interaction and interconnection of all elements of the material and technical base and infrastructure of hotels in accordance with current requirements;

Broad implementation of new technologies in production and service delivery processes, including interpersonal communication and operational interactions;

Developing and enhancing the high level of professional skills and competencies of hotel staff, thereby creating a welcoming and high-quality hospitality environment;

Organizing and aligning service quality management processes based on the hotel's specific needs and internationally recognized quality standards.

The object of the hotel classification assessment system is to measure the level of services provided to consumers and evaluate service quality. This enables the identification and elimination of shortcomings within the existing system. From this perspective, integrating such a system into the management framework for tourism competitiveness and attractiveness would be a rational approach.

The primary goal of this integration is to promote the wide application of unified scientific, technical, socio-economic, and legal management methods, and to implement a comprehensive set of targeted measures. It is advisable to implement this system nationwide and across all regions of the country.

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